

How to avoid exchange rate disturbances on a growth path. A joint analysis from development macroeconomics and the supermultiplier

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Abstract

With rare exceptions, economies that started from a backward position have been unable to join the growth track. The apparent reasons are structural deficiencies and recurrent crises in key economic variables such as exchange rates, interest rates, and inflation. “Developmental macroeconomics” tries to understand and solve these problems. One of the milestones of such a growth model is the book by Bresser-Pereira, Oreiro, and Marconi, which celebrates its 15th anniversary this year. This paper considers macroeconomic development from the perspectives of classical economics and the supermultiplier growth model. By relating it to the endogenous money hypothesis, we suggest creating an international (crypto)currency to sustain industrial growth and address problems arising from abrupt movements in exchange rates, interest rates, and inflation.

Keywords: Developmental macroeconomics; supermultiplier growth model; endogenous money; exchange rate instability; international currency.

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1. Introduction

Capitalist market economies constitute dual (asymmetric) systems in which advanced countries coexist with less developed countries (LDCs). Economists in LDCs complain about the difficulty of competing on equal terms — i.e., using the same technology — at least in industrial sectors where production is highly standardized. To make matters worse, recurrent disturbances in the exchange rate, interest rate, and price level penalize LDCs. Advanced countries also have grounds for concern. To whom will they export if LDCs are unable to pay?

This paper examines the challenges faced by low- and (particularly) middle-income countries, like Brazil. For this endeavour, we join forces between two emerging growth models: *developmental macroeconomics* and the *supermultiplier*. The masterpiece of the first group is *Developmental macroeconomics: New developmentalism as a growth strategy* (Bresser-Pereira, Oreiro, & Marconi, 2015). Oreiro, Martins da Silva & Dávila-Fernández provide a valuable update of this book: “A *New Developmentalist* model of structural change, economic growth and middle-income traps” (Oreiro, 2020). The first monographic book on the *SM* is: *The Supermultiplier. A cornerstone of the new macroeconomics* (Dejuán, 2023). Extensions of the *SM* model, after introducing the *money endogeneity* hypothesis, appear in the special issue of the *Review of Political Economy*, edited by Barbieri, Dejuán, Paribonni, & Summa. These papers were published later as a book (Barbieri, 2025)

In our opinion, both models share common elements rooted in the *Surplus Approach*, as expounded by Pasinetti (1981). The columns of this eclectic approach are:

- 1) The Classical theory of production, distribution, and value, introduced by Ricardo (1817) and updated by Sraffa (1960).
- 2) The Keynesian-Kaleckian principle of effective demand and the multiplier that captures induced consumption (Keynes (1936), Kalecki (1971)). The supermultiplier incorporates the acceleration principle, which adds induced investment.
- 3) The post-Keynesian hypothesis of money endogeneity². Today, in advanced and middle-income countries, more than 90% of the means of payments are bank-money. It is created through loans, whose counterparts are debt and deposits. These loans respond to a private demand and are endorsed by the monetary expansion of the Central Bank.
- 4) The relevance of the economic structure and institutions in growth analysis. Latin American structuralism pioneered this approach. Kaldor followed the track and inspired the post-Keynesian school that highlights productivity gains³. Schumpeter (1912) focused on innovative entrepreneurs.

Both *DM* and the *SM* highlight the key role of exports as the engine for sustainable growth. In our opinion, they share the following traits:

² Although the idea is an old one, the money endogeneity hypothesis has been popularized by post-Keynesian economists: Kaldor (1958), Moore (1988), Graziani (2003), Lavoie (2014), Rochon and Rossi (2017).

³ Prebisch (1949), Furtado (1952), Hirschman (1958), Emmanuel (1972). Kaldor (1961).

- (1) Free and competitive international trade forces firms to be more efficient. This is the origin of the trade gains.
- (2) For every single country, the main advantage of international trade is the possibility to import cheaper and better consumer and investment goods.
- (3) Exports are equally important because they allow countries to pay for imports. Otherwise, international trade could not be sustainable.
- (4) The production of goods for exports drives domestic output and employment. The computation of these effects is one of the SM's contributions.
- (5) For better or worse, movements of the economic structure and the exchange rate influence the performance of international trade and the growth path. This is an essential contribution of DM.

About the structure of the paper. Section 2 analyses the quantity and price systems of a competitive economy —the “real economy,” so to speak. Section 3 introduces money and finance. To optimize the functioning of the global economy, we suggest creating a cryptocurrency to facilitate global industrial payments. Section 4 concludes

2. The real economy.

Technology, distribution and prices of production

We are analyzing a competitive market economy. Competition in the classical sense is identified with the pressure to increase productivity and adjust prices to the falling unit costs. The result is the long-run tendency towards a uniform profit rate⁴.

Our economy integrates four *vertically integrated sectors* producing four final goods. Intermediate goods and capital amortization would be represented by indirect labour and indirect fixed capital⁵.

The *quantity structure* of the imaginary economy we are analyzing consists of four commodities.

- q_1 : Tradable capital goods for final investment.
- q_2 : Tradable consumption goods for final consumption.
- q_3 : Non-tradable personal services.
- q_4 : Exploitation of scarce natural resources and tradable goods derived from them.

According to the Sraffian price system, given technology (the labor and capital coefficients, l and k) and given one of the distributive variables, a competitive economy determines the other distributive variable and relative prices. In a closed economy, it makes

⁴ Eatwell (1982) explains the meaning and relevance of “perfect” neoclassical competition and “sufficient” classical competition.

⁵ Pasinetti (1973) explains the meaning and the advantages of dealing with VIS. The *Leontief's inverse* is the operator that allows the transit from the real industries of an Input Output Table to the vertically integrated sectors.

sense to treat the wage rate agreed in collective bargaining (w) as given. In an open economy, where capital moves faster than labour, we'd better treat the worldwide profit rate (r^*) as given.

In the following mathematical system (1), we have four equations (one for each good) and four unknowns: 3 relative prices (since $p_1=1$) and the wage rate (w). Asterisks identify the known variables.

$$(1) \quad \begin{aligned} p_1 &= 1 = w \cdot l_1^* + r^* \cdot p_1 \cdot k_{11}^* \\ p_2 &= w \cdot l_2^* + r^* \cdot p_1 \cdot k_{12}^* \\ p_3 &= w \cdot l_3^* + r^* \cdot p_1 \cdot k_{13}^* \\ p_4 &= w \cdot l_4^* + r^* \cdot p_1 \cdot k_{14}^* \end{aligned}$$

Changes in distribution alter production prices. More important is the impact of technological improvements. Competition forces a price adjustment to reflect the lower unit cost of production. Demand movements affect market prices but only in the short run. In the long run, market prices tend to gravitate toward the unit cost of production that includes the general rate of profit.

The general level of production and employment.

Our quantity system reflects the Keynesian-Kaleckian principle of effective demand. The level of output in period t is a multiple (M) of the expected autonomous demand (A) for the same period. Sraffa would add: “‘expected’ at the normal prices derived from the unit cost of production”. The price-equation system given in (1) is implicit in the Keynesian quantity system. At this moment, we had better adopt a macroeconomic perspective. We refer to “baskets of goods” whose elements keep their initial shares for the time being. By construction, the money price of each basket is one⁶

The supermultiplier (SM) captures both induced consumption ($c \cdot Y$) and induced investment ($h \cdot Y$). The second one refers to the production of and the demand for *capacity-creating investment*. In the autonomous demand vector, we include *residential investment* by households and *modernization investment* by firms, i.e., the demand for capital goods that transform productive capacity rather than increase it. According to the *acceleration mechanism*, capacity-creating investment depends on the expected growth of persistent demand (γ) and the optimal capital/output ratio (k) that conveys a normal degree of capacity utilization. Sraffians use to normalize it at the unity ($u^*=1$) and consider that it plays as a gravity center. In short, $h=k \cdot \gamma$. Autonomous demand also includes real public expenditure and exports.

The supermultiplier is expressed by the following equation:

$$(2) \quad SM = \frac{1}{1-c(1-t)-h} = \frac{1}{\sigma}$$

The first ratio measures the drag on induced demand. The second computes the same figure as the inverse of the income not linked to induced demand (σ). It amounts to the income share of proper autonomous demand (z). $\sigma = 1-c(1-t)-h = z$.

⁶ A disaggregated analysis is necessary for certain purposes. In any case, the Keynesian multiplier and the Sraffian supermultiplier can be derived from input-output tables (Dejuán, 2023, ch. 10).

Suppose that all the elements of autonomous demand grow at γ . The increase in aggregate demand would be a (super)multiple of the new autonomous demand.

$$(3) \quad \Delta Y_t = SM \cdot \Delta Z_t (1 + \gamma)$$

When the elements of Z grow at different rates, the expected growth of autonomous demand will be a weighted average of such rates (the weights are proportional to their share in Z).

$$(4) \quad \gamma = g_{z1} \left(\frac{z_1}{Z} \right) + g_{z2} \left(\frac{z_2}{Z} \right) \dots$$

If the expected growth of autonomous demand is *persistent* enough, all the elements of aggregate demand will follow suit. The same happens for the production factors (L , K). This allows us to write the following equations, where causality runs from left to right.

$$(5) \quad (g_z =) = g_d = g_y = g_L = g_K = g_p$$

A remarkable result of the SM model is that the potential or warranted rate of growth (g_p) also adapts to the expected acceleration of demand. Harrod's warning about the extreme instability of the multiplier-accelerator model fades away in the SM model. In the short run, firms are supposed to increase capacity utilization (Δu) to serve an increasing demand. To return to the normal degree, firms will increase the income share of expansionary investment (Δh). The final result is an acceleration of economic growth, with a return to normal capacity. A new potential rate has emerged.

Normal or potential capacity does not mean full employment. Yet, the capacity to absorb a growing labour force will be enhanced if entrepreneurs envisage new markets for new products. Or the existent ones, conveniently improved.

Endogenous money in the Schumpeterian – Post-Keynesian tradition.

The money-endogeneity hypothesis is one of the cornerstones of post-Keynesian economics, including those inspired by the French School of the Circuit (Kaldor, 1958; Moore, 1988; Graziani, 2003; Lavoie, 2014, ch. 4; Rochon, 2017). We should remember, however, that great economists assumed money endogeneity at all times (Tooke, Marx, Wicksell and Keynes –before and after the *General Theory*–). In our opinion, Schumpeter (1912) deserves special mention because he highlights the connection between the endogenous money hypothesis and the SM model (although he never mentioned either).

In the first chapter of his 1912 book, he warns that competitive capitalist economies tend to stagnate. Entrepreneurs lack the incentive to change their routines when their actual profit rate is enough to cover the opportunity cost. The impetus to grow comes from innovative entrepreneurs who, seeking higher profit rates, modernise their investments to produce new goods or traditional ones more efficiently. In chapter 2, Schumpeter explains that the first task of innovative entrepreneurs is to visit their bankers and convince them that they would benefit from financing the new projects.

If banks agree, they will create money by crediting the entrepreneur's bank account: $\Delta M^f = \Delta DEP = \Delta CR$ (where M^f is the money supply, DEP stands for deposits, and CR for loans).

Bank money is “destroyed” when the entrepreneur’s debt is cancelled. The “endogeneity” of money means that bank’s money adapts to the demand from private borrowers. At the turn, legal money (the monetary base issued by the CB) accommodates the monetary reserves required in our fractional reserve system.

The autonomy of banks allows them to grant loans to purchase fixed-supply assets (e.g., land or equity). A speculative bias is usually present in these loans. Werner (1997) considers that in most financial crises, credit growth is systematically above output growth. The same relation has been denounced by schools so opposed as the Austrians (Mises, 1912) and the post-Keynesians (Minsky, 1982).

3. Money and financial variables. Inflation, interest rates and exchange rates.

The one-economy–one-currency world was merely an excuse to analyze the price and quantity systems of a capitalist, competitive market economy. The appropriate image for our research purposes is the separation of two asymmetric economies and two asymmetric currencies. We are thinking of a middle-income country like Brazil competing with advanced economies like the USA and the EU. The two currencies are: $\beta\$,$ an international currency, and $R\$,$ a local currency acceptable only for domestic transactions in region B.

Region B is a politically independent country with its own currency and a Central Bank (CB^b) that controls it. The basic tasks of B’s government are (1) Promoting conditions for an industrial sector capable of competing internationally. (2) Controlling inflation. (3) Avoiding an excessive appreciation /depreciation of $R\$.$

Two asymmetric economies. The advanced core and a less developed country.

“The specialisation of an economy influences the actual performance and dynamics”. This is the basic tenet of *structuralism*. The origin of this hypothesis, like many others related to economic growth, lies in Latin America in the 1950s: Prebisch (1950) and Furtado (1952). In the 1960s, N. Kaldor popularised it among the Cambridge group through the cumulative causation method –the virtuous and vicious circles so common in the economy. Thirlwall (1979) introduced the balance-of-payments-constraint hypothesis. It focuses on the income elasticity of exports/ imports in each country.

DM argues that the easiest specialization for LDCs is the extraction of their natural resources. Such specialization may boost productivity in $q_4,$ but being an isolated sector, the effects may not spill over into the national economy. In addition, we can expect capital flows from advanced countries into natural resource-related activities. These flows may appreciate the domestic currency ($R\$$) and depress the exports of industrial goods. The “Dutch disease”!

Bresser-Pereira, Oreiro and Marconi (2015) are firm supporters of the industrialization of less developed countries. It is the first step toward ensuring sustainable growth that leads to genuine development of the country. Pasinetti (1981) would applaud this initiative and recall that, as far as industrial goods are concerned, nothing prevents them from being fully competitive. According to him, the first task of an LDC is to replicate the production methods of advanced countries and compete openly with them through the learning-by-doing process.

Asymmetrical exchange rate regimes.

We define the nominal exchange rate (E) as the units of the international currency ($\beta\$$) exchanged against one unit of the local currency in B ($R\$$). $E = \beta\$ / R\$$. An appreciation of the LDC's currency (an increase in E) implies that more units of $\beta\$$ have to be paid to obtain one unit of $R\$$. The *real exchange rate* is obtained by adding the nominal price index ratio to the previous ratio: $e = E \cdot (P^b / P^a)$. When the inflation rate is systematically higher in B, $R\$$ should depreciate to maintain its purchasing power. Market forces will push in this direction, as people try to get rid of the local currency. In the following sections, we shall assume a constant price level to focus on the two relevant issues at this moment.

Is there a unique equilibrium of the exchange rate (E^)?* This question should be answered in the negative. The trade balance can be in equilibrium with different exchange rates. A depreciation of $R\$$ enhances the exports of certain goods but obliges us to pay more for basic imports such as energy and investment goods⁷.

Even if we could agree on a “reasonable” exchange rate, can we expect market forces to drive it? The *law of one price* provides a positive answer, yet we should be aware of its empirical limits. If there were only one tradable good, the equilibrium exchange rate would equalize the price of this good measured in the same currency. The bad news is that tradable commodities number in the millions. The good news is that production prices (equations 1 above) serve a similar function when we consider a basket of industrial goods whose proportions remain constant for a time. The international prices of industrial goods (p_1 and p_2 nominated in $\beta\$$) are supposed to coincide with the production cost. The lower wages paid by firms in B will offset the structural advantages of A, such as the faster adoption of new technologies that B's firms will eventually copy.

Bresser-Pereira, Oreiro, and Marconi (2015) propose fixing the exchange rate at the level that ensures the international competitiveness of the basket of industrial goods. Oreiro, Martins da Silva and Dávila-Fernandez (2020) clarify that there is no single equilibrium exchange rate. Yet politicians can avoid “exchange rate disturbances” by setting the real exchange rate at a level compatible with the desired/normal current account deficit-to-GDP.

I propose a more radical proposal under Keynes's inspiration. At the Bretton Woods Conference (1944), Keynes proposed the creation of a new currency (*the bancor*) related to a weighted basket of natural resources. In the following pages, I use Keynes' name for the international currency, but, being in the internet era, I opt for a *cryptocurrency* supervised by an international agency. Our primary concern is to avoid the exorbitant privilege that the US has enjoyed after fixing the American dollar as the global currency.

The international agency responsible for the bancor would create the digital money by granting loans to purchase globally traded commodities. The amortization of these loans would imply money destruction, as the theoreticians of money endogeneity explain. Loans for non-productive assets should be forbidden. Credit expansion could not be systematically above output growth.

4. Conclusions

⁷ In addition, we should consider the impact on E of current transfers (interest payments), and the financial flows registered in the capital account.

Capitalist economies exhibit a “duality” in the national paths of growth, an asymmetry that has increased over time. The usual image confronts “core *versus* periphery”, or “advanced *versus* less developed countries”, in particular middle-income country like Brazil.

The Developmental Macroeconomics (DM) school and the Supermultiplier (SM) model have guided our analysis. Both approaches emphasize the importance of exports in ensuring a sustainable growth path. The SM learns from the DM about the problem of exchange rate disturbances and offers insights into Sraffian-Pasinetti systems of prices and quantities. Competitive economies tend towards prices of production that cover the unit cost, with a uniform profit rate. Quantities adjust to the supermultiplier times the *expected autonomous demand at their production prices*.

Pasinetti (1981) insists that the primary and main task of LDCs is to replicate the production techniques used by advanced countries. This is relatively easy for industrial goods, whose production is highly standardized. Both core and peripheral firms will compete effectively in the international market if they operate the dominant technology most efficiently and can sell commodities at the unit cost.

In the international economy, exchange rate disturbances pose problems for middle- and low-income countries. In our opinion, the only way to avoid exchange rate disruptions is to adopt a single currency for international trade in industrial goods. The cost for LDCs of dispensing with their own currency stems from the risk of competing openly in global markets. Most people are afraid of such a risk. Yet, they should learn from history that it is the best way to improve the international competitiveness of developing countries—the only way to keep the innovative thrust.

In our proposal, there is no proper exchange rate for industrial transactions, because they are performed in a single international currency. Yet, if industrial goods are sold at their production prices, we can affirm that each commodity has a fair exchange rate, one that ensures the same price everywhere when valued in the same international currency.

Political independence allows developing countries to have their own currency for domestic use (personal services and other non-traded goods and services). Their independent central banks are supposed to control the national price level, the interest rate and the exchange rate. Economists in rich countries usually disregard the curse of inflation and exchange rate disturbances. Economists in LDCs should explain to them the havoc caused recurrently by such disturbances.

Indeed, the institutional reforms we propose will face opposition from vested interests. Yet, social changes ultimately depend on social demands. In our opinion, we are witnessing an increasing desire to eliminate the exuberant privileges of the USA derived from the Bretton Woods agreements in 1944. I propose an official international cryptocurrency that frees money creation from government pressures. We'd better ensure bank competition on credit expansion under the supervision of a global agency.

Let us conclude this paper with the last paragraph of Pasinetti's (1981) book. It has inspired me in our joint task with Bresser-Pereira, Oreiro, and Marconi to overcome the artificial obstacles to genuine development, both for less developed countries and advanced economies.

“For an industrial nation, wealth is not a stock of material goods (which only represent the external expression of it) – it is a stock of technical knowledge. (...) It may be consoling to think that the wealth brought to us by the industrial age is a much more favorable type of wealth, than the old one, to relations among people and nations. For, if, in the pre-industrial world, the main way for a country to increase its wealth was to dominate and exploit its neighbours, today it has become *to emulate them and do better*” (p. 276)

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